

SCADA Communication in Smart Grid Photovoltaic Plant

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Abstract – This study uses a network simulation software application as working tool to create a wireless communication technology in a smart grid system. the aim of this study is to apply the proposed PV plant which is integrated into the smart grid system and its communication and components coordination through Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition Systems (SCADA). The proposed system is a large-scale photovoltaic (PV) plant hybrid with diesel generator integrated into microgrid. It is a two-way communications of PV inverters using SCADA. The role of communication and control system includes PV voltage and current output control. The microgrid consists of 8MW and 18MW PV plants, 15 MW diesel generator, and 10 MW residential load and 0.16 MVA industrial load. The 24-hours data is expected to be monitored and neglectable the distance on SCADA through the implemented model. However, as the concept is built in the MATLAB Simulink platform, the system has an offset time at 10 hours of its operational. The output voltage and current show the rushed trend at the beginning of the system but getting steady as the system runs. As the results, this effected to the trend of the active power of the components of smart grid, which tends to remain steady and slower.

Keywords: Smart grid; SCADA; two-way communication; PV plant; diesel generator

Introduction

According to reference [1], “Smart grid can be defined as a concept for transforming the electric power grid by using advanced automatic control and communications techniques and other forms of information technology. It integrates innovative tools and technologies from generation, transmission and distribution all the way to consumer appliances and equipment.” This concept integrates energy infrastructure, processes, devices, information and markets into a coordinated and collaborative process that allows energy to be generated, distributed and consumed more effectively and efficiently. Many technologies that are used in the smart grid are already implemented in other areas of industry such as sensors and wireless networks.

In order to increase the monitoring, protection, and optimization of all grid components, which is including generation, transmission, distribution, and consumers, the smart grid employs two-way communications, digital technologies, advanced sensor and processing infrastructure, and software capabilities. By utilizing improved and controlled large-scale integration of renewable energy sources, the smart grid minimizes greenhouse gas emissions. To avoid unanticipated frequency and voltage variations, this large-scale integration necessitates the use of powerful distributed control algorithms [2]-[4]. Energy storage systems, grid-to-customer communication, and improved algorithms for grid generation and loading forecasts all necessitate a two-way communications system to assure full coordination between generated and consumed energy. This lower grid energy losses, peak demand, and energy prices. Energy consumers can obtain accurate real-time prices and bills thanks to two-way connectivity. The grid operator can receive real-time information from consumers regarding the amount of electricity consumed. The successful operation of a smart grid requires a dependable

real-time information flow between all grid components. A dependable and effective communication infrastructure, whether wired or wireless, can be used to accomplish it. Low prices and easy connectivity to remote and inaccessible regions are two advantages of wireless infrastructure over wired one. However, when wireless infrastructure interferences with other communications and electromagnetic fields, as well as battery dependency, then the system is downsides. The ancient power grid's existing communication infrastructure was built to handle only one-way power transmission from central power plants to users, with minimal efficiency and information sharing.

The data acquisition from a restricted number of sensors located in the main transmission and distribution points, the transmission of a limited number of control signals, and the identification of defects are the main functions of the ancient power grid communication systems. Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition Systems (SCADA) [5] are used to collect data. The smart grid, on the other hand, has a much higher number of sensors and actuators than the ancient one. They are deployed at all levels of the grid, including power plants and substations, generators, transformers, and customers. The sensors are used to collect data and convey information between equipment and data centres. The actuators are utilized to control all grid components optimally. The smart grid needs have modern, dependable, and strong communication infrastructure capable of providing real-time secure communications in order to handle such massive data flows. To ensure a high rate of information transmission, the communication infrastructure must have a large bandwidth. In addition, the communication infrastructure must be self-healing and adaptable to changes automatically [6].

According to [6], The communication of smart grid infrastructure can be built within three different types of networks: home area networks (HAN), neighbourhood area networks (NAN), and wide area networks (WAN) (WAN). HAN is normally deployed and operated in a small (tens of meters) space, such as a house or a small office. In comparison to the other two networks, the HAN has a modest transmission data rate of hundreds of bits per second (bps). A HAN consists of a broadband Internet connection shared by numerous users via a wired or wireless modem in a typical deployment. It allows computers, mobile devices, and other devices to communicate and share resources over a network connection. All smart home gadgets that consume energy, as well as smart meters, can be connected to HAN in a smart grid deployment. The data from the devices is collected and sent to the smart meters through HAN. HAN enables for more efficient energy management in the home.

NAN is deployed and operated over a large region of hundreds of meters, which is equivalent to a few city blocks. Several HANs can be connected to a single NAN, and they send data on how much energy each house uses to the NAN network. This data is delivered to Local Data Centers through the NAN network for storage. This data storage is necessary for charging consumers as well as data analysis for recognizing energy generation-demand patterns. The transmission data rate of NAN is up to 2 Kbps. PLC, Wi-Fi, and cellular technologies can all be used to implement the NAN.

The WAN, which is made up of multiple NANs and LDCs, is deployed and operated over a large area of tens of kilometers. Furthermore, WAN is used to communicate amongst all grid components, including the operator control center, main and renewable energy generation, transmission, and distribution. The WAN has a very high data rate for transmission data, up to a few Gbps. Ethernet networks, WiMAX, 3G/LTE, and microwave transmission can all be used to create a WAN. The illustration of smart grid communication infrastructure can be seen in Figure 1.

Many firms and countries are working on smart grid communication technology and protocols at the same time [7]. It is critical to guarantee that multiple smart meters, communication protocols, and infrastructures are all integrated. This could be accomplished by creating global standards that will be approved by all firms and organizations interested in smart grid development around the world. The most common standards for smart grid communication such as 802.15.4, ISO 1802, IPv4, DNP3, IEC61970, etc. [8] [9].

The two-way communications network architecture for the remote monitoring of large-scale PV plants based on the IEC 61850 Standard. The IEC 61850 is a communication standard and data model for substation communication and control that is uniform and standardized. It is now the de facto communication standard

for the automation of substations on the global market. The use of IEC61850 has been expanded to wind power, hydro power, and decentralized power systems for several years. It focuses on communications within the PV power plant's substations. The IEC 61850 standard specifies how power system equipment should structure data in a uniform manner across all types and brands of devices. Because the devices can configure themselves, this removes a lot of the time-consuming non-power system configuration work. The object definitions can then be extracted from the device over the network by the IEC 61850 client program. As a result, there is a significant reduction in the cost and work required to configure an IEC 61850 device [8] [9].

This research is developed to design a concept of PV plants which communicate through SCADA system. The role of communication and control system in this project includes PV output control, active power control and the wireless communication based in smart grid system is used in a network simulation software application as a working tool. The proposed system in the design is large-scale photovoltaic (PV) plant which is integrated into the microgrid that has diesel generator as well. The paper is structured as follow. Section one is described about smart grid, and the wireless communication technology that is used. Section two is described the proposed design of integrated PV plants into smart grid. Section three is described the results of the simulation of the proposed design and analyse the given scheme. Finally, in section four, the conclusion of the proposed design is given.

Methods

The PV plant consists of solar arrays, inverters, feeders, buses, single substation, and a control center. Also, the involved components, i.e., transformer, collector bus, collector feeder, and PVG are illustrated in Figure 1. Since it was designed for LANs in electrical substations, it primarily uses the TCP/IP protocol and an Ethernet link as a communication medium [9]. The architecture layers, which are the PV power system layer, the communication network layer, and the application layer, respectively.

Figure 1. Standard layout for smart grid communication architecture [10].

By adapting the developed concepts in reference [11] for the structure of single PV plant, and reference [9] for the smart grid PV plant configuration. The suggested communication network design for large-scale PV plants is made up of three layers: the PV power system, the communication network, and the application layer. The IEC 61850-7-420 Standard is used to represent the PV plant [12]. SCADA systems are crucial for remote monitoring and control of solar power plants and PV output control, active power control and collecting sales data. It allows the control centre operator to analyse performance, discover operation difficulties, and identify faults during atypical conditions, ensuring a dependable and safe operation for PV plant subsystems. The voltages and currents are monitored at the microgrid level on SCADA system. Also, the PV plant's overall performance is monitored at the microgrid level on SCADA system as well [13] [14] [15].

The model of the microgrid included the SCADA system has been built and simulated in MATLAB Simulink. Figure 2 illustrates the hybrid microgrid (combination of two PV plants 8 MW and 18MW, respectively, 15MW-diesel generator). The system utilized and served 10MW residential load and 0.16 MVA industrial load. The 24 hours data is expected to be monitored and neglectable distance on the SCADA system through the implemented model.

Figure 2. Proposed microgrid PV plant.

Results

The microgrid is divided into four important parts, a diesel generator, acting as the base power generator; 2 PV plants to produce renewable energy; the last part of the system which is the load of the grid. The size of the microgrid represents approximately a community of a thousand households during a low consumption day over a year. The diesel generator balances the power consumed and the power produced. We can determine the frequency deviation of the grid by looking at the rotor speed of its synchronous machine. The size of the area covered by the PV farm makes efficiency of the solar panels and the irradiance data. The load is composed of residential load and an asynchronous machine that is used to represents the impact of an industrial inductive load (like a ventilation system) on the microgrid. The residential load follows a consumption profile with a given power factor. The asynchronous machine is controlled by a square relation between the rotor speed and the mechanical torque.

The parameters of real-time monitored parameters namely the output voltage and current of the PV plants and diesel generator. Figure. 3 illustrates the output voltage (a) and current (b) for 8MW PV, Figure. 4 illustrates

the output voltage (a) and current (b) for 18MW PV and Figure. 5 illustrates the output voltage (a) and current (b) for 15MW diesel generator. As the system has an offset time at 10 hours of its operational, the trend of the active power of the system's components has the tendential of getting to slower. The system depends on SCADA to operate.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3. Output voltage and current of 8MW PV plant.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4. Output voltage and current of 18MW PV plant.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5. Output voltage and current of 15MW diesel generator.

Conclusion

The concept that has been discussed in this paper refers to the operating system of a large-scale PV plant and a diesel generator that integrated into the microgrid. The microgrid system operated through SCADA and the wireless communication technology which coordinated the data of the parameters roles as the mobile monitor tools. The microgrid consists of 8MW and 18MW PV plants, 15 MW diesel generator. The system utilized and served 10MW residential load and 0.16 MVA industrial load. The 24 hours data is expected to be monitored and neglectable distance on the SCADA system through the implemented model. The output voltage and current have been trended of the PV plants and diesel generator, respectively. The output voltage and current show the rushed trend at the beginning of the system. Thus, the trend of the active power of the components of smart grid tend to steady and slower. This proposed system could be implemented to the PV plant as it is already simulated through the Simulink MATLAB platform.

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